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***Deliverable 5.1- Product Demonstration and Field Trial
Results***

A. Dissemination Level

PU	Public
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

B. Document details

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0. Executive Summary

Fastprk2 has developed a smart on-street parking system to control regulated spots with occupancy sensors, aiming to improve the user experience and the mobility management in cities.

This deliverable provides the overview of the work done in the last months of the project (M21-M26) towards **the completion of the pilot campaign** foreseen in the EC-GA, with the aim to **validate the final solution** before the official market launch. The document contains a detailed description of the pilot deployments in selected infrastructures, the performed tests to validate the product, and an analysis of the lessons learnt during the last project stage.

The feedback received from different stakeholders have been partially integrated in this document, while the business evaluation of the gains introduced by the solution is fully set out in the deliverable D6.2, since it directly shapes the core part of the exploitation strategy to be implemented beyond the EC action.

Since the deliverable is labelled as “Demonstrator” in the EC-GA, Worldsensing provides here direct evidence of the attained results through a set of images and operational details of each pilot venue and the achieved results. Besides, raw data of the parking events have been published at a public repository, so that they can be freely reused by data scientist in line with the Open Science strategy launched by the European Commission.

1. Introduction

Fastprk2 has developed a leading end-to-end parking management technology with advanced features compared to the competitors' solutions. To make full use of the project efforts, the improved functionalities of the new product, ranging from the certified parking occupancy detection to advanced services, have been merged with the mobility platform of WorldSensing.

The project has allowed attaining a complex system that involves hardware and software, and it has been specifically designed to enrich the product portfolio of WorldSensing while keeping the equilibrium between the technological breakthroughs and the commercial priorities of the company.

In this deliverable, we present (i) the full **details of the pilot campaign** at different locations, (ii) the **analysis** of the obtained **results** and their evaluation, and finally (iii) a high-level **critical thought** of the **status of the new solution** at the completion of the project.

Last but not least, we point out that most of the **raw data** acquired during these months have been made public in **ZENODO**¹ so that, it can be reused by the data scientist community in the future in line with the **Open Science** strategy promoted by the EC.

As stated in the deliverable D4.1, the activities of WP4 and WP5 have been merged in an iterative process to dynamically improve the different releases of the Fastprk2 prototypes towards the successful achievement of the final product. This approach has partially conditioned the pilot campaign, as it will be signified in the document.

The varying maturity levels of the elements which have progressively been integrated in the Fastprk2 architecture has made advisable adopting this agile strategy with the objective to avoid any unnecessary delay during the action implementation.

This deliverable is structured as follows:

- **Section 2.** A high-level overview of the pilot campaign. The full context, as well as the applicable legal framework, were already provided in the deliverables D7.1 and D4.1.
- **Section 3.** Description of each pilot with updated details of the operational infrastructure in place, evidence of their performance and analysis of the obtained results.
- **Section 4.** Aggregated assessment of the pilots' results and their evaluation against the expected technical and business outputs.
- **Section 5.** Wrap-up and strategic analysis with the lessons learnt from the pilots. This section is directly linked to the business plan presented in the deliverable D6.2.

This document is a review of intensive and multifaceted work involving many different departments within the company. For this reason, it is almost impossible to provide full details of each development without tedious and long wording.

On the contrary, and since the deliverable is labelled as "Demonstrator" in the EC-GA, WorldSensing provides here direct and selected evidence of the attained results through a set of images and operational details of each pilot venue. **Further details are available upon request.**

From a reporting point of view, the present status of the tasks and associated milestones listed in the EC-GA is summarized in the table below:

¹ <https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=fastprk2&sort=mostrecent>

Table 1 - Status of the project tasks and milestones linked to the pilots

WP	Task	Comment	Milestone	Status
4	T4.1 Robust parking management prototype in specific versions	Architecture defined in WP3 can be easily accommodated to specific requirements from the customers	MS7 TRL7 operational tests results	Completed
	T4.2 Modules dependency	The dependency between the different modules and data sources has been defined and validated in lab-controlled demos		
	T4.3 Complexity analysis and policies definition	Set of policies and rules to assess the real deployments, the expected functionalities and the hardware and software needs are drafted. Refined in WP5		
5	T5.1 Field configuration for pilot deployment	Actions for each pilot trial are completed	MS8 TRL8 operational tests results	Completed
	T5.2 Product quality demonstration	Tests running in real-scenarios. Direct interaction with stakeholders.		
	T5.3 Solution assessment			

2. Pilots project campaign: description and groundwork

Fastprk2 is a market-oriented project which has **resulted in a technology ready for commercialization at M26**. To achieve this goal, the final solution has been previously validated in real-test scenarios, aiming to reach the TRL8 level with proven guarantees in all its aspects. With this in mind, a detailed solution assessment involving technical and commercial aspects has been conducted during the last part of the project.

According to the EC-GA provisions, an intense piloting campaign in different (European and American) venues has been envisaged with a three-faceted objective:

1. **Gathering real data** to improve the technical implementation of the final product release;
2. Acquiring the necessary **know-how** to guarantee the **replicability** of the proposed solution for different environments and scenarios;
3. Raise the **awareness of the solution** by the future clients, receiving from all of them a detailed and direct assessment of its performance.

Worldsensing has, therefore, enjoyed a **unique opportunity to test the effectiveness of the project results** and receive an enriching **feedback from stakeholders** before the real product launch.

The stakeholders engaged to support the project pilots (*Table 2*) have been selected for their complementary background, combining developers of traffic management technologies, trading companies of smart-parking solutions and public and private end-users. This has allowed Worldsensing acquiring a representative overview of the strengths and weaknesses of Fastprk2 solution from different but complementary perspectives.

Table 2 - Fastprk2 pilots during the validation phase. Figures and locations

Pilot #	Stakeholder	Venue	# Sensors
1	Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC)	Barcelona (Spain)	12
2	ENGIE- Cofely Fabricom	Antwerp (Belgium)	25
3	SWARCO	Wattens (Austria)	47
4	AFAPARK	Paris (France)	5
5	City Parking Group S.A.	Grudziadz (Poland)	30
6	Parking Sense	Los Angeles (USA)	110

Compared to the status presented in the deliverable D4.1, the following two changes in the pilots' plan have been introduced during the final stage of the tests campaign:

1. **Location of the Polish pilot:** Grudziadz city has been finally selected to meet the requirements of City Parking Group S.A (local partner in Poland);
2. **Integration in the pilot list of Los Angeles (USA)** thanks to a commercial opportunity with Parking Sense (see the deliverable D6.2).

These two modifications have allowed **increasing the impact of the project**, as it will be discussed in the document.

As described in the deliverables D3.1 and D3.2, **Fastprk2 architecture is modular and adaptable**. Therefore, each specific pilot has required an **accommodation process** to offer the desired functionalities that the end-users seek.

In fact, all pilots supported by the project have shared the **Concept 1** of Fastprk2 (new sensor with improved parking detection) while **Concept 2** (parking management platform) and **Concept 3** (ITS) have been adapted to the specific needs in an interactive process with the stakeholders (tasks T4.1 and T5.1).

In the frame of the EC action, **Fastprk2 pilots** have allowed validating the attainment of **Concept 1** with real data (sensor nodes), while the rest of functionalities (**Concept 2 & Concept 3**) have been evaluated by mainly using **simulated and synthetic data**².

Worldsensing has been committed throughout the project to perform a professional management of ethical issues potentially emerging in the pilot campaign: the company had already identified relevant concerns during the preparation of the EC-GA and simultaneously, the EC carried out an ethics scrutiny of the proposal with the objective of verifying the respect of ethical principles and the relevant legislation.

Regarding Fastprk2, the research entailed specific ethical implications involving human subjects. In this context, the pilots' deployments were designed according to the ethical provisions summarized in the deliverable D7.1

Two different kinds of end-users have been engaged in the project pilots to validate the functionalities provided by the Fastprk2 solution: **citizens and technology/commercial stakeholders**.

As regards the former, it must be pointed out that the detection mechanism of the parking spots does not entail any personal data, but the physical detection of vehicles without the identification of the citizens in any case. For this reason, anonymous data are used only for statistical and predictive purposes, and they are integrated into the platform on an aggregated level.

Nevertheless, and with the aim to avoid any controversy about the consent of citizens to participate in Fastprk2, **the tests' areas have been clearly identified using a public notice** whose content has been agreed with the local authorities on a case-by-case basis. This point is explicitly stated in the agreement with the pilots' managers in line with the EC-GA provisions. In this way, citizens (drivers and pedestrians) have always known in advance that they were taking part in the pilot study, implicitly consenting their participation in Fastprk2 when they chose a parking spot in the area.

On the other hand, the implementation of enforcement tools has been redesigned from its initial conception: Worldsensing has proposed an alarm system so that local authorities move a supervisor to punish the offender on-spot if necessary. The identification of law violators directly through Fastprk2 technology is beyond the scope of the project and may collide with National legal regulations. Details of the enforcement service have been given in the deliverable D3.1.

Fastprk2 allows the **data storage of parking events** without the identification of citizens and their lifestyle patterns.

Regarding the technology stakeholders, they have provided feedback about the pilot results (full details in the deliverable D6.2). Despite this has been done at an institutional level, Worldsensing has kept a direct contact with physical persons (employees) to gather the information. Their contact details are explicitly given in this document.

Table 3 - Detail of H-requirements for citizens and pilots' stakeholders

End-users	Recruitment	Identification	Informed Consent	
			Procedure	Template
Citizens	Open and random	Anonymous	Public notice in the street	Pilot dependent
Technology/commercial stakeholders	Selected for their profile	Table 2	Pilot agreement with WS	Agreement shown in previous deliverables

Personal data such as name and telephone have been handled according to the applicable legislation on Data Protection.

² ITS services tested in the pilots have been operating with simulated and synthetic data. Only the traffic monitoring tool has used real data provided by a third party (Tomtom) through a public API. In this particular case, Worldsensing does not receive any information from users, but the aggregated information of the traffic flow per street.

In this sense, Worldsensing has acted to comply with the regulations on Personal Data Protection. The fine details of the actions taken in this subject are provided in the final Periodic Report of the project.

3. Pilots deployment: operational details & results

In this chapter, the main characteristics of each project pilot and the obtained results regarding Concept 1 (sensor detection performance) are presented in a catch-eye approach, trying to summarize the scope and main outputs³. Images of the installed sensors and the pilots' venues are provided in the corresponding annexes of this deliverable. Those already shown in the deliverable D4.1 have been intentionally omitted to avoid unnecessary duplicities.

Pilot 1: UPC (Barcelona, Spain) – Operational Details

Third Party General Details	Institution / Company	Universitat Politècnica de Barcelona (UPC)
	Main contact point	
	Other contacts done to implement the deployment (i.e. teleconf, visits on premises, etc)	

Location Details	Venue (address and geographic coordinates)	UPC Calle Jordi Girona, 31 08034 Barcelona (Spain) GPS coordinates: 41.3889784344569,2.1138623938485956
	Google maps images and photos of the area (+ sign)	See deliverable D4.1, Annex I
	Infrastructure details	
	Number of sensors	12
	Number of gateways	1
	Number of other physical elements (PC, Server, etc)	Own resources from the Third Party

³ The performance and assessment of the elements linked to Concept 2 and Concept 3 are provided in an aggregated way at the Chapter 4 of the document.

Installation Details	Company in charge	<p>Worldsensing pays for the installation.</p> <p>Installer: <i>Ciurans Group SCP</i> <i>Avda. Can Prat, 20</i> <i>08100 Mollet del Vallès (BCN)</i> <i>CIG J61898227</i></p> <p>The installer is an official provider selected by WS internal purchase procedures</p>
	Images of the installation process and the final result	See deliverable D4.1, Annex 1

Operational Details	Services to be tested	Parking Occupancy Prediction
		Sustainable Traffic Model
		Anomaly Detector Service
	Evidence of the normal operation	See deliverable D4.1, Annex 1
Duration of the pilot programme	5 months	

Pilot 1: UPC (Barcelona, Spain) – Results

This installation consists of 9 regular car-sized parking slots and 3 oversized parking slots allocated for large vehicles performing unloading/loading tasks. Appended to the physical installation of the sensors at UPC premises, a dedicated instance of the Fastprk-2 software and services have simultaneously been deployed at (<https://fp2-barcelona.worldsensing.com/mb/app/>). Worldsensing has granted full access to the UPC contact points and the EC-PO. Some screenshots of this platform are shown in the table below, but further details and even the access credentials are available upon request⁴.

It should be pointed out that the UPC pilot was the **first one after the lab-development stage** of the new technology; it has been mainly used to fix the countless bugs and errors found in a non-controlled environment.

⁴ The credentials to log in UPC software instance have been sent to the PO in parallel communications.

Thus, the results achieved in this pilot have not been considered significant to validate the final detection accuracy of the sensors, but to early set the basis for specific improvements in the solution, such as the release of a second version of the nodes' firmware (see the deliverable D3.3).

The pilot' location, which is just a few minutes away from Worldsensing's office, has also facilitated the accurate follow-up and supervision of the new technical features by the company' staff, becoming an excellent testbed.

View of the parking occupancy in the Barcelona's pilot area. The pop-up shows the detailed information of the spots.

View of the traffic flow in the Barcelona's pilot area. The pop-up shows the traffic forecast for the next hour.

The **operation of the sensors** has been validated by an outside company in a campaign divided into two stages. In the first one, the quality and integrity of the obtained data have been monitored and analysed; while in the second, the so-called event commissioning has matched the system output with actual parking events (car entering or leaving the parking slots) during a significant period (one week). This latter stage done partly manually is considered the ultimate proof that the system is working as expected.

The analysis of the solution in this pilot has been based on **652 parking events (each day averaging 120)**.

The table below shows a screenshot of some figures collected during the campaign, which has revealed a mean **detection error of 8.3%** with regard to the total number of events. As a first approximation, this value is far from acceptable, but going into details the following useful information has been concluded from the pilot experience:

- 1) **The error source mainly concentrated on the large vehicles zone.** Since only one sensor per spot has been installed, this might not be enough to cover the 100 % of the parking area if smaller vehicles are parked there. This easily leads to false occupancy readouts depending on the vehicle size and position. A total of 13 events is explained by this situation;
- 2) **The number of errors** not ascribable to the former cause was **higher in rainy days**: after a detailed assessment, it was concluded that humidity and water droplets in the IR window of the node resulted in an unstable behaviour of the new tandem sensor during the detection operation. A total of 12 events is explained by this situation;
- 3) The vast majority of the **remaining errors** were originated by the packet loss caused due to **communication link problems**. A total of 16 events is explained by this situation;
- 4) Only a **small proportion** (13) of error events remains **unexplained**, and they could be directly ascribable to intrinsic problems coming from the node design.

The table below shows the error events in the UPC pilot classified into the different categories:

Table 4 - Results of the pilot campaign in Barcelona: error events broken down according to origin

Types of errors (UPC-Barcelona). Commissioning campaign		
Type	Description	Total
Detection failure (large spots)	The sensor does not cover the entire parking spot area. False readout if the vehicle is not placed exactly over it	13
Unstable IR + magnetic readouts	Water droplets on the IR window. Unstable behaviour. Problem with the detection algorithm	12
Communications	Packet loss due to the location of the gateway and communication problems	16
Other	Unexplained error	13
Total Error		54
Total Events		652
Total Error %		8,3%
Total Error % (unexplained only)		2,0%

In view of these results, it was assumed that the following actions were required to improve these figures in future experiences:

- 1) **Define better the parking areas**, installing in all of them enough sensors to cover potential blind spots;
- 2) **Improve the detection algorithm** to avoid “water interferences”. To that end, a second version of the sensor firmware became necessary.
- 3) Make sure that the communication was good enough to **minimize coverage problems**.

Pilot 2: ENGIE (Antwerp, Belgium) – Operational Details

Third Party General Details	Institution / Company	ENGIE
	Main contact point	
	Other contacts done to implement the deployment (i.e. teleconf, visits on premises, etc)	

Location Details	Venue (address and geographic coordinates)	Antwerp downtown: Van Wesenbekestraat 2060 Antwerpen, Belgium GPS coordinates: 51.220222, 4.420752
	Google maps images and photos of the area (+ sign)	See deliverable D4.1, Annex 2
	Infrastructure details	
	Number of sensors	25
	Number of gateways	1
	Number of other physical elements (PC, Server, etc)	Own resources from the Third Party

Installation Details	Company in charge	Worldsensing pays for the installation. Installer: Engie Kontichsesteenweg 25 – 2630 Aartselaar - BELGIUM The installer is directly the client (third party partner).
	Images of the installation process and the final result	See deliverable D4.1, Annex 2

Operational Details	Services to be tested	Traffic Forecasting
		Parking Occupancy Prediction
		Multimodal Service
		Guidance and Recommendation Service
		Sustainable Traffic Model
		Anomaly Detector Service
Evidence of the normal operation	See deliverable D4.1, Annex 2	
Duration of the pilot programme	5 months	

Pilot 2: ENGIE (Antwerp, Belgium) – Results

A particular feature of this pilot has been the **sustained exposure of the nodes to moisture** (Atlantic climate), **the extremely noisy environment** due to the nearby tram tracks), the **high turnover** of the parking occupancy and the **absence of spots delimitation marks**. Actually, the sensors have been installed in a commercial cobblestone street in Antwerp downtown which aggregates most of the adverse conditions for the correct operation of the sensors. It should be pointed out that in similar locations, the use of the first version of Fastprk sensors resulted in detection accuracies utterly disappointing, hindering the practical use of smart parking technologies.

Appended to the physical installation of the sensors, a dedicated instance of the Fastprk-2 software and services have been deployed at (<https://fp2-antwerp.worldsensing.com/mb/app/>), granting full access to the ENGIE contact and the EC-PO. Some screenshots of this platform were shown in the deliverable D4.1, but further details and even the access credentials are available upon request⁵.

Summary of the Antwerp’s commissioning campaign. The detection accuracy is at first glance disappointing.

⁵ The credentials to Antwerp software instance have been sent to the PO in parallel communications.

Since the pilot experience has chronologically run almost in parallel to the UPC's one, the same problems were found there as well. With a total **error of 9,5 %** of the total events, the detection issues had presumably the same origin than in Barcelona. Nevertheless, and despite this disappointing accuracy figure, the overall result of the Antwerp installation can be **labelled as positive** for the following reasons:

- 1) The **installation** of the sensor nodes **in road traffic streets** was **successfully completed**. The new design of the node did not entail any further difficulty in terms of civil work compared to the commercial version of Fastprk;
- 2) The **corrective measures** to eliminate the **water leakage** inside the node (resin coating) was assessed as the **right choice** since this problem was eliminated;
- 3) The **overall detection rate** was much better than the first version of Fastprk (magnetic sensor only). This results indirectly validates the tandem detection approach of Fastprk2, despite there was room for improving the system performance;
- 4) The **ITS and the software platform operated perfectly** in a large city like Antwerp, establishing the first tangible contact of the global solution with a potential customer.

Pilot 3: SWARCO (Wattens, Austria)

Third Party General Details	Institution / Company	SWARCO AG
	Main contact point	
	Other contacts done to implement the deployment (i.e. teleconf, visits on premises, etc)	

Location Details	Venue (address and geographic coordinates)	SWARCO premises: Blattenwaldweg 8 6112 Wattens, Austria GPS coordinates: 47.288276, 11.587236
	Google maps images and photos of the area (+ sign)	See the deliverable D4.1, Annex 3
	Infrastructure details	
	Number of sensors	47
	Number of gateways	1
	Number of other physical elements (PC, Server, etc)	Own resources from the Third Party

Installation Details	Company in charge	<p>Worldsensing pays for the installation.</p> <p>Installer:</p> <p>P&O di des of Perkmann Geom. Georg Linee guide a led via Constantino, 4 Konstantinerweg Nr. 4 39050 Fie allo Sciliar Völs am Schlern (Italy)</p>
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		The installer has been selected by the client (third party partner) following its internal procurement rules.
	Images of the installation process and the final result	See the deliverable D4.1, Annex 3
Operational Details	Services to be tested	Parking Occupancy Prediction
		Guidance and Recommendation Service
		Sustainable Traffic Model
		Anomaly Detector Service
	Evidence of the normal operation	See the deliverable D4.1, Annex 3
Duration of the pilot programme	3 months	

Pilot 3: SWARCO (Wattens, Austria) – Results

After correcting the problems resulting from both the first firmware version installed at the sensors and the water leakage in the node boxes, the **pilot campaign reached the decisive phase** with the pilots in Austria and France. There, the almost-final release of the Fastprk2 technology was tested under the direct supervision of two giants like **SWARCO** and **AFAPARK**.

In this particular pilot (Wattens, Austria), the deployment of new sensors was completed at **SWARCO premises**, a controlled area where new mobility concepts such as the e-cars management are tested at present. Since it is not open to the general public, like a city street, the gateway was installed guaranteeing the best quality communication coverage but without applying the preventive measures to avoid vandalism, which is a typical requirement of urban installations. It must be pointed out that during the pilot campaign, the **weather conditions** were **extreme** (cold and snow), which resulted in a **litmus test** to validate the Faspark2 performance.

Appended to the physical installation of the sensors, a dedicated instance of the Fastprk2 software and services have been deployed at (<https://fp2-wattens.worldsensing.com/mb/app>), granting full access to the SWARCO contact and the EC-PO. Some screenshots of this platform were shown in the deliverable D4.1, but further details and even the access credentials

are available upon request⁶. Since SWARCO is a potential competitor of Worldsensing in the Mobility sector, some functionalities of the new software have been deliberately restricted for them.

View of the SWARCO premises. Those areas in which Fastprk2 sensors are installed are marked in green.

View of the parking area at SWARCO premises in which the Fastprk2 pilot has been conducted. The study area is duly indicated with the project public notice.

⁶ The credentials to SWARCO software instance have been sent to the PO in parallel communications.

(Left) Fastprk2 gateway installed in the SWARCO parking area. (Right) Faspk2 sensor covered by snow and ice.

View of the parking occupancy in the Wattens' pilot area. The software has deliberately some functionalities disabled.

The performance of the sensors was tested in a 4-day commissioning campaign with **excellent results** compared to the two previous experiences in Barcelona and Antwerp. Despite the adverse weather conditions, the new firmware allowed increasing the accuracy of the sensors in line with the EC-GA provisions, while no water was found inside the boxes after the pilot.

Table 5 - Results of the pilot campaign in Wattens: total errors are indicated for the 4-days commissioning

Pilot SWARCO (Wattens). Commissioning campaign			
Day	Events no.	Error no.	% Accuracy
1	45	0	100,0%
2	84	1	98,8%
3	121	1	99,2%
4	159	1	99,4%
Total	409	3	99,3%

The **accuracy of the sensors** was found to be as high as **99,3%** with only three errors during the commissioning campaign. With an excellent gateway coverage, they errors are fully ascribable to detection problems which suggest that the firmware algorithm could be further improved to overcome adverse weather conditions (water and ice on the IR-window).

Pilot 4: AFAPARK (Bouffemont, France)

Third Party General Details	Institution / Company	AFAPARK
	Main contact point	
	Other contacts done to implement the deployment (i.e. teleconf, visits on premises, etc)	

Location Details	Venue (address and geographic coordinates)	AFAPARK GPS N49.044141 E2.321854 www.afapark.com
	Google maps images and photos of the area (+ sign)	See Annex 4
	Infrastructure details	
	Number of sensors	6
	Number of gateways	1
	Number of other physical elements (PC, Server, etc)	Own resources from the Third Party

Installation Details	Company in charge	Worldsensing pays for the installation. Installer: Microzanjas The installer is a regular provider of Worldsensing selected following the internal procurement rules of Worldsensing
	Images of the installation process and the final result	See Annex IV of deliverable D4.1

Operational Details	Services to be tested	Parking Occupancy Prediction
		Guidance and Recommendation Service
		Sustainable Traffic Model
		Anomaly Detector Service
	Evidence of the normal operation	See Annex IV of deliverable D4.1
	Duration of the pilot programme	3 months

Pilot 4: AFAPARK (Bouffemont, France) – Results

The characteristics of the pilot at Bouffemont was equivalent to those of SWARCO but a smaller scale: the sensors with the second firmware release were installed in a private parking and an excellent communication coverage was achieved in the entire test area.

Appended to the physical installation of the sensors, a dedicated instance of the Fastprk-2 software and services have been deployed at (<https://fp2-bouffemont.worldsensing.com/mb/app>), granting full access to the AFAPARK contact and the EC-PO. Some screenshots of this platform were shown in the deliverable D4.1, but further details and even the access credentials are available upon request⁷.

Unlike for the rest of the pilots, the **validation** of the Fastprk2 technology was **directly performed** by the **third-party partner**, who conducted its own commissioning campaign. Despite not providing the full technical details of the results, **AFAPARK** representatives have independently validated that the detection accuracy was in line with the expectations (see *Annex I*). This has confirmed the findings of Wattens' pilot and consequently the performance of the Fastprk2 technology.

⁷ The credentials to Bouffemont software instance have been sent to the PO in parallel communications.

Pilot 5: City Parking Group (Grudziadz, Poland)

Third Party General Details	Institution / Company	City Parking Group SA
	Main contact point	
	Other contacts done to implement the deployment (i.e. teleconf, visits on premises, etc)	

Location Details	Venue (address and geographic coordinates)	28 Mickiewicza, 86-300 Grudziadz, Poland GPS coordinates 53.490854, 18.753113
	Google maps images and photos of the area (+ sign)	See Annex II
	Infrastructure details	
	Number of sensors	30
	Number of gateways	1
	Number of other physical elements (PC, Server, etc)	Own resources from the Third Party. 1 VMP installed at the pilot area

Installation Details	Company in charge	Worldsensing refunds for the installation to City Parking Group which has used its own provider for civil works.
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Operational Details	Services to be tested	Traffic Forecasting
		Parking Occupancy Prediction
		Multimodal Service
		Guidance and Recommendation Service
		Automatic Payment Service
		Automatic Enforcement Service

		Sustainable Traffic Model
		Dynamic Pricing Service
		Anomaly Detector Service
	Evidence of the normal operation	See Annex II
	Duration of the pilot programme	3 months

The pilot at Grudziadz has been the first chance to materialize a **commercial opportunity beyond the Fasprk2 action** with a well-known partner such as City Parking Group (CPG). Having reached the maturity level found in Austria and France, the deployment of Fastprk2 sensors in this pilot was conceived as a **real and complete demonstrator** of the new functionalities developed in the project, which should lead to commercial actions in the future.

Thirty sensors and a VMP (Variable Message Panel) were installed in Grudziadz downtown (see images in *Annex II*). The installation and the functioning of the sensors were borne by the local partner, and a three-day commissioning campaign was successfully conducted in which the sensors outputs were compared twice a day with the real occupancy status.

Appended to the physical installation of the sensors, a dedicated instance of the Fastprk-2 software and services have been deployed at (<https://fp2-grudziadz.worldsensing.com/mb/app/>), granting full access to the City Parking Group contact and the EC-PO. Some screenshots of this platform are shown in *Annex II*, but further details and even the access credentials are available upon request⁸.

Pilot area in Grudziadz downtown. The red spot indicates the exact location of the Fasptk2 gateway.

⁸ The credentials to Grudziadz software instance have been sent to the PO in parallel communications.

(Left) General view of the parking area in Grudziadz downtown. (Right) Detailed view of the Fastprk2 notice.

Pilot 5: City Parking Group (Grudziadz, Poland) - Results

The **accuracy results** coming from the local partner were, however, **extremely disappointing** at first glance. The overall figure after the three-day campaign was only **85,8 %** which was far below the expected value and is not consistent with the results observed in both Austria and France.

Again, a detailed analysis of the attained results revealed the origin of this divergence. In *Table 7*, the events monitored during one day of the campaign are shown. The main source of errors are the following ones:

1. Some of the sensors experienced **calibration problems** despite their readouts were correct from a practical point of view. CPG labelled the status of these sensors as wrong for the sake of consistency;
2. The **parking spots** areas were **not well signalled**, like in Barcelona and Antwerp. This fact led to false free-state status outputs even though the parking spots were really occupied by vehicles.

Considering these two undesired situations and manually removing their effect from the overall accuracy result, the detection performance was in all cases higher than 95%, which is a value closer to the expected one.

The main lessons learnt from this pilot regarding the Concept 1 of Fastprk2 are:

1. The **final accuracy** figure is highly **dependent** on both the **installation layout** of the sensors and the result of the **calibration** tasks. Inadequate attention to these two aspects can hinder reaching the expected accuracy values even if the node may potentially reach a better performance.
2. **Real installations in cities** are far more **complex** than those in controlled areas (i.e. SWARCO premises). Additional variables not controlled such as communication issues can affect the behaviour of the entire deployment.

In short, Grudziadz was a **reality check** that forced Worldsensing to pay much **more attention to secondary aspects** if the expected accuracy values in the next installations wanted to be attained.

Table 6- Results of the pilot campaign in Grudziadz: events during the commissioning (1-day)

Round 1			Round 2		
Sensor	Real	Server	Sensor	Real	Server
1	FREE	FREE	1	FREE	FREE
2	FREE	OCCUPIED	2	FREE	FREE
3	FREE	FREE	3	FREE	FREE
4	OCCUPIED	OCCUPIED	4	OCCUPIED	OCCUPIED
5	FREE	FREE	5	OCCUPIED	FREE
6	FREE	FREE	6	OCCUPIED	OCCUPIED
7	FREE	FREE	7	FREE	FREE
8	FREE	FREE	8	FREE	FREE
9	OCCUPIED	OCCUPIED	9	OCCUPIED	OCCUPIED
10	OCCUPIED	OCCUPIED	10	OCCUPIED	OCCUPIED
11	FREE	FREE	11	OCCUPIED	OCCUPIED
12	OCCUPIED	OCCUPIED	12	OCCUPIED	OCCUPIED
13	FREE	FREE	13	OCCUPIED	FREE
14	FREE	FREE	14	FREE	FREE
15	OCCUPIED	OCCUPIED	15	OCCUPIED	OCCUPIED
16	OCCUPIED	OCCUPIED	16	OCCUPIED	OCCUPIED
17	FREE	FREE	17	OCCUPIED	OCCUPIED
18	FREE	FREE	18	FREE	FREE
19	FREE	FREE	19	FREE	FREE
20	FREE	FREE	20	FREE	FREE
21	FREE	FREE	21	FREE	FREE
22	FREE	FREE	22	OCCUPIED	OCCUPIED
23	OCCUPIED	OCCUPIED	23	FREE	FREE
24	FREE	FREE	24	OCCUPIED	OCCUPIED
25	FREE	OCCUPIED	25	FREE	FREE
26	FREE	FREE	26	OCCUPIED	OCCUPIED
27	OCCUPIED	FREE	27	OCCUPIED	FREE
28	FREE	FREE	28	FREE	FREE
29	FREE	OCCUPIED	29	FREE	FREE
30	FREE	FREE	30	FREE	FREE
INCIDENCES		14,3%	INCIDENCES		10,7%

Pilot 6: Parking Sense (Los Angeles, US)

Third Party General Details	Institution / Company	Parking Sense
	Main contact point	
	Other contacts done to implement the deployment (i.e. teleconf, visits on premises, etc)	NA

Location Details	Venue (address and geographic coordinates)	(1) Wardlow North 3440 North Pacific PO. Long Beach Parking facility (2) Wardlow South 3420 N Pacific PI Long Beach (3) Willow St 2750 West American Avenue. Long Beach.
	Google maps images and photos of the area (+ sign)	See Annex III
	Infrastructure details	
	Number of sensors	110
	Number of gateways	2
	Number of other physical elements (PC, Server, etc)	Own resources from the Third Party.

Installation Details	Company in charge	Worldsensing has supported the installation costs of a subcontractor (Belco Elecnor Electric), a company which fulfils the legal requirements of LA authorities.
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Operational Details	Services to be tested	All services replicated. They have not been the scope of the pilot
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	Evidence of the normal operation	See Annex III
	Duration of the pilot programme	3 months

The **pilot at Los Angeles** was not initially scheduled in the EC-GA and it resulted from a **unique opportunity** derived from the regular activity of Worldsensing: Parking Sense, one of the big players at a global scale in parking management, won a huge tender to install smart parking technologies in some of the LA metro stations. However, the selected technical partner was unable to meet the requirements in due time, and Worldsensing was chosen as an alternative to moving forward with the project.

In a first stage, 79 Fastprk-1 sensors were installed in two different areas (17th SMC Parking facility and North Hollywood) without environmental noise in a purely commercial project. As expected, a high accuracy rate (96.66%) was achieved therein overcoming the 95% minimum target fixed by the customer. This successful result paved the way for the Fastprk2 pilot, which configured a much more demanding scenario: **three different areas** highly affected by the **electromagnetic noise** coming from the proximity of the railway tracks were offered to **test the Fastprk2 technology** in extremely adverse conditions (see *Annex III*). There, some of the installed sensors could be put to the real litmus test.

Appended to the physical installation of the sensors, a dedicated instance of the Fastprk-2 software and services have been deployed at (<https://fp2-losangeles.worldsensing.com/mb/app>), granting full access to the EC-PO. This software was internally used by Worldsensing with the main purpose to assess the replicability of the solution in non-European regions.

Some screenshots of this platform are shown in *Annex III*, but further details and even the access credentials are available upon request⁹.

Pilot 6: Parking Sense (Los Angeles, US) - Results

A 4-days commissioning campaign in the three areas has been conducted to validate the operation and accuracy of the installed devices. In overall terms, the **results have been successful**, substantially exceeding the target fixed by Parking Sense. The breakdown of the events categories is the following one:

Table 7- Results of the pilot campaign in Los Angeles: accuracy values achieved during the commissioning

Area		Events no	Errors no	Accuracy
1	Wardlow North	715	15	97,90%
2	Wardlow South	594	14	97,64%
3	Willow	1100	14	98,73%
TOTAL	LA Metro	2409	43	98,22%

This result is extremely good taking into account the adverse boundary conditions of the pilot, and it represents a huge progress for the adoption of smart parking solutions in noisy areas which remained forbidden before Fastprk2. In fact, the source of errors was mainly ascribable to two non-technical reasons:

⁹ The credentials to Los Angeles software instance have been sent to the PO in parallel communications.

1. **Some parking spots did not have clear boundaries (painted marks).** This problem has repeatedly appeared in previous pilots like Antwerp and Grudziadz;
2. **Drivers did not respect the parking areas** even though they are correctly marked (see figure below).

Parked car in the middle of two marked parking spots: this leads to false readouts of the sensors.

Excluding the effect of the two abovementioned points, the accuracy rate in LA nearly has reached the highest value confirming that the **Concept 1** has been successfully achieved once the sensor node had become mature enough.

4. Consolidated assessment of the pilots' results

In this chapter, a **joint review of the pilots' results** is provided with particular attention to the different concepts identified in the EC-GA. As shown in Chapter 3, the technology tested in the different pilots has not been homogeneous from a maturity point of view. For this reason, a storyline must be built to correctly interpret the results.

Regarding the **Concept 1 (parking space sensor)**, the pilots' experience has shown:

1. The **appropriateness of the new tandem IR and magnetic sensor** to operate in extremely noisy locations in which pure magnetic sensors exhibited disappointing results in the past;
2. In **controlled areas** (private parking premises) in which the communication coverage is optimal, and the spots are well marked, sensor **accuracy values of virtually 100%** are achieved;
3. The deployment of the **technology in real scenarios** (i.e. streets in cities) are **affected by manifold problems**: some of them are technological such as communication issues and failures of the detection algorithm, but the most important ones are directly related to the sensor distribution on the roadway and the delimitation of the parking areas;
4. The appropriate treatment of the abovementioned risks results in **Fastprk2 deployments showing accuracy values above 98% even though the environmental conditions are adverse** (extreme weather conditions and high electromagnetic noise). There is always a **residual error ascribable to the drivers' behaviour** hard to eliminate.

For all these reasons, the overall **assessment** regarding **Concept 1** is that the new parking sensor searched at the beginning of the action has been **achieved** despite there is further scope for improvement in some points once the project is finished.

As far as the **Concept 2 (parking management platform)** is concerned, the objective of the action was to develop a more efficient and effective customer experience over parking and traffic management through a platform able to integrate and combine different data sources.

In the frame of the pilots' analysis, the main scope of this deliverable, the **architecture and the internal operation of the platform has not been directly assessed but their function**. On this point and related to the EC-GA provisions, the following features have been achieved during the pilots' implementation:

Integration layer: the former management Fastprk interface (left) has been integrated into the Mobility platform of the company (right) capable of ingesting different data sources and inputs coming from heterogeneous devices.

New GIS module: The Mobility platform of Worldsensing, the cornerstone of the UX of Fastprk2, has been improved with a new system to enhance the usability of the solution in an intuitive way.

Fastprk-2 database, fusion module and Big Data analytic tools: the platform makes possible to build in an easy way a database with the historical parking events, which is later used to perform occupancy predictions using neuronal networks-based technologies. The data gathered during the pilots' campaign are available at ZENODO repository: <https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=fastprk2&sort=mostrecent>

As a result, and without going into detail of the platform details provided in other deliverables, it is safe to say that the **Concept 2** foreseen in the EC-GA has also been **successfully achieved** by the end of the Fastprk2 action.

Finally, the **Concept 3 (transport services and BI tools)** developed in the frame of the project have been indirectly validated by means of the performance assessment of the different Fastprk2 software instances created at the pilot level. As previously stated, each one of the pilots' partners has previously defined their own requirements, except for SWARCO and Parking Sense; and the available ITS in their instance have been adapted by Worldsensing accordingly. The assessment task has been finally conducted by Worldsensing in close collaboration with all of them.

Table 8 summarizes the main reasons to select the final list of pilots and the difficulty level to deploy Fastprk2 technology. The rationale behind this table has been discussed in the deliverable D4.1.

Table 8 - Rationale to select the pilots' locations (chronological order)

Location	Reason	Scenario (difficulty)
Barcelona	1. Proximity to Worldsensing (Barcelona)	Easy
	2. Facilities for the first proofs	
	3. Controlled area (no road traffic)	
Antwerp	1. Urban area	Critical
	2. Electromagnetic noise (nearby tram traffic)	
	3. Commercial contact with ENGIE	
Paris	1. Controlled area in a partner with expertise in parking exploitation	Medium
	2. Opportunity to compare Fastpr2 vs Fastprk	
Wattens	1. Extreme weather conditions	High
	2. Feedback from a direct competitor	
Grudziadz	1. Commercial contact with City Parking Group	High
Los Angeles	1. Commercial opportunity	Critical
	2. Electromagnetic noise (nearby rail tracks)	
	3. Fastprk2 beyond EU limits	

Considering the characteristics of each one of the above-mentioned pilots, the deployed services have been tailored to the third-party requirements. The available ITS at each pilot is provided in the tables below:

ITS (Service)		Barcelona		Rationale
		Y	N	
1	Traffic Forecasting		X	Location at university campus without road traffic
2	Parking Occupancy Prediction	X		Location at a loading / unloading area. The service will provide useful insight to delivery trucks
3	Multimodal Service		X	Parking spots used by freight companies. Consequently, the possibility to leverage on the public transportation does not apply herein
4	Guidance and Recommendation Service		X	No DMS available
5	Automatic Payment Service		X	The parking spots are of free use
6	Automatic Enforcement Service		X	The parking spots are of free use
7	Sustainable Traffic Model	X		UPC is environmentally conscious, and they appreciate having this service in the pilot
8	Dynamic Pricing Service		X	The parking spots are of free use
9	Anomaly Detector Service	X		Service installed by default to operate the Fastprk2 platform

		Antwerp		
ITS (Service)		Y	N	Rationale
1	Traffic Forecasting	X		The pilot is installed in downtown with severe road traffic problems. The service is particularly useful in this location
2	Parking Occupancy Prediction	X		Location in a mixed area with loading areas and regular parking spots. The service will provide useful information to the city operator
3	Multimodal Service	X		Location in downtown. End-users may be interested in combining private- and public transportation
4	Guidance and Recommendation Service	X		The local partner in charge of the installation are manufacturers/installers of DMS panels. A commercial opportunity may arise
5	Automatic Payment Service		X	Service not requested by the pilot partner
6	Automatic Enforcement Service		X	Service already in place with the partner's own solution
7	Sustainable Traffic Model	X		Service installed by default in urban locations to rise the environmental awareness
8	Dynamic Pricing Service		X	Service not requested by the pilot partner
9	Anomaly Detector Service	X		Service installed by default to operate the Fastprk2 platform

		Wattens		
ITS (Service)		Y	N	Rationale
1	Traffic Forecasting		X	In-door traffic area without road traffic.
2	Parking Occupancy Prediction	X		Service requested by the pilot partner
3	Multimodal Service		X	Service not requested by the pilot partner
4	Guidance and Recommendation Service	X		Service requested by the pilot partner
5	Automatic Payment Service		X	The parking spots are of free use
6	Automatic Enforcement Service		X	The parking spots are of free use
7	Sustainable Traffic Model	X		Service installed by default in urban locations to rise the environmental awareness
8	Dynamic Pricing Service		X	The parking spots are of free use
9	Anomaly Detector Service	X		Service installed by default to operate the Fastprk2 platform

		Paris - Bouffemont		
ITS (Service)		Y	N	Rationale
1	Traffic Forecasting		X	In-door traffic area without road traffic.
2	Parking Occupancy Prediction	X		Service requested by the pilot partner
3	Multimodal Service		X	Service not requested by the pilot partner
4	Guidance and Recommendation Service	X		Service requested by the pilot partner
5	Automatic Payment Service		X	The parking spots are of free use
6	Automatic Enforcement Service		X	The parking spots are of free use
7	Sustainable Traffic Model	X		Service installed by default in urban locations to rise the environmental awareness
8	Dynamic Pricing Service		X	The parking spots are of free use
9	Anomaly Detector Service	X		Service installed by default to operate the Fastprk2 platform

ITS (Service)		Grudziadz		Rationale
		Y	N	
1	Traffic Forecasting	X		This pilot has been conceived as a first real and complete demonstrator of Fastprk2 technologies. For this reason, the final version of all the services have been tested in a real-environment, reaching TRL9. Physical elements like an VMP have also been physically deployed in the city.
2	Parking Occupancy Prediction	X		
3	Multimodal Service	X		
4	Guidance and Recommendation Service	X		
5	Automatic Payment Service	X		
6	Automatic Enforcement Service	X		
7	Sustainable Traffic Model	X		
8	Dynamic Pricing Service	X		
9	Anomaly Detector Service	X		

Last but not least, it must be pointed out that the assessment of **ITS in Los Angeles** has been considered a **secondary task**. In fact, the main pilot motivation was to validate the performance of the sensors in extreme and harsh environments, while the associated services have been merely used to illustrate that they could be easily deployed anywhere in the world easily and quickly. Actually, this has been achieved after some months of hard work necessary to convert Fastprk2 into a real and replicable product. Further details about this are provided in the deliverable D3.3.

Table 9 - Summary of ITS tested in the pilots

ITS (Service)		Pilot				
		Barcelona	Antwerp	Paris	Wattens	Gdynia
1	Traffic Forecasting		X			X
2	Parking Occupancy Prediction	X	X	X	X	X
3	Multimodal Service		X			X
4	Guidance and Recommendation Service		X	X	X	X
5	Automatic Payment Service					X
6	Automatic Enforcement Service					X
7	Sustainable Traffic Model	X	X	X	X	X
8	Dynamic Pricing Service					X
9	Anomaly Detector Service	X	X	X	X	X

In the following lines, the performance each one of the services listed in the Table 9 is briefly presented in an aggregated approach.

Traffic Monitoring & Forecasting.

The real-time monitoring of the traffic flow in cities has been extensively **validated** during the pilot campaign. Tomtom has been chosen in all cases as the data provider, but any other could be used as an alternative (i.e. Google). As shown in the first figure (Barcelona), the system easily allows selecting some streets of interest, whose incoming data will be later used for the traffic forecasting action. In fact, the main difference between Fasprk-2 traffic monitoring and other well-known systems like Google Maps relies on the fact that these data later train the AI tool supporting the forecasting service in the background. Since data are gathered through an API by doing periodic calls to the provider system, the total cost of monitoring the 100% of a city like Barcelona can be considerable. This potential problem will be discussed in Chapter 5 of this document from a business perspective.

As far as the forecasting is concerned, the **AI tools** developed together with **ATEKNEA** have proven to be powerful enough to **correctly predict** the traffic conditions at different time frames. By the default, the 1-hour time horizon has been considered the most adequate to allow the authorities establishing flexible corrective actions to guarantee a fluid traffic flow in the monitored area. As shown in the second image (Barcelona), the prediction (yellow lines) matches almost perfectly with the real-traffic conditions after 1-hour once the neuronal network is correctly trained. This usually takes some days and it is highly dependent on how complex the traffic is. In this sense, Fig 3 shows that in Antwerp, the accuracy of the prediction is only 78% after a long period of training since at that time the downtown was highly affected by construction works leading to a chaotic scenario difficult to read and model. Due to this uncertainty, the high-value of the so-call “anomaly score”, an internal KPI directly related to the Anomaly Detector Service (Fig.3), indicates that the incoming data are quite random. On the contrary, for Barcelona’s pilot (Fig.2), the same KPI indicates no anomalies or in other words, real-time data in agreement with the historical ones.

Fig.1: Pilot area in Barcelona. The real traffic monitoring service shows info about the status in Av. Diagonal.

Fig.2: Pilot area in Barcelona. The forecast traffic service shows the expected conditions in Av. Diagonal in one hour horizon.

Fig.3: Pilot area in Antwerp. The forecast traffic service shows the expected conditions in one hour, alerting about anomalous traffic conditions compared to the historical data. This is ascribable to civil work effects in the city.

Parking Occupancy Prediction.

For the parking service, both the **real-time monitoring** and the **prediction** functionalities have been completely **unified** in a new interface fully integrated into the Mobility platform of Worldsensing, without eliminating the standard Fastprk calibration and management software suite, which still runs in the background for some specific actions (screenshots shown in the deliverable D4.1). The new service tries to show in a catch-eye approach the real-time occupancy status of the different parking sensors using a self-sustaining colour code (green – free, red – occupied) which is constantly updated (Fig.1, Wattens).

By clicking in a specific sector, a detailed information of the occupation status is shown as well as a **6-hour forecast** (given in percentage of the total spots). As in the traffic case, the sensors readouts are used to train the AI tools behind the forecast service, which depends on the total number of events, and the complexity of the underlying occupancy patterns. In the Fig.2 it is shown how the system reproduces the real occupancy status in Wattens (red lines), providing future values quite close to the reality (yellow lines). In this particular case, it is clearly observable how the parking is almost empty from July 28th to July 29th (weekend). Again, this matching exercise between real sensor readouts and predictions is highly dependent on the behaviour of the partners: in areas with extreme rotation (Fig.3. Grudziadz), the system can spot trends but not the occupancy peaks that are continuously occurring. Nevertheless, it is expected that the AI tool will refine these results as time goes by and more data are gathered in the system.

Fig.1: Pilot area in Wattens. The parking occupancy status in the pilot area is indicated, showing a high availability of free spots.

Fig.2: Pilot area in Wattens (high zoom image). The parking occupancy forecast in 6-h is shown. The system provides high quality predictions.

Fig.3: Pilot area in Grudziadz. Despite the system anticipates quite well the mean occupancy values per sector, it cannot predict the short occupancy peaks derived from a high parking turnover.

Multimodal and Guidance and Recommendation Services.

These two services have barely evaluated in the frame of the pilots' campaign. The developed app to implement them (see the deliverable D3.2) has however been provided to the partners for the use test. These services are considered an add-on functionality that can be easily offered to citizens in which Fastprk2 is adopted. In this sense, they are rather an awareness tool for the advantages of adopting smart mobility habits / solutions than a real technological breakthrough compared to the SoA technologies.

Sustainable Traffic Model.

Just as in the case of the former services, the sustainable traffic model has been only partially evaluated in the pilots' campaign. Despite being an excellent tool to trigger specific alarms for the city operators once the pollution levels reach dangerous thresholds, its adoption will be a long-term matter: at this moment there are other major problems to be solved according to the authorities' point of view. In this sense, its acceptance by the partners have been good but its use has been merely symbolic during the project implementation.

Fig.1: Pilot area in Barcelona. Pop-up showing the pollution levels in one specific measurement station. As this being written, it was not operative (no data).

Anomaly Detector Service.

As stated in former deliverables, the final implementation of this service has been different from the first conception. In the current version of Fastprk2, this service is a tool running in the background which enriches some of the other services (please see the traffic forecasting one). Besides, it allows performing a detailed analysis of the data entering the platform (see Annex IV), which can be later used by city operators to design strategies and policies aiming at the optimization of the urban mobility.

Dynamic Pricing and Automatic Payment and Enforcement services

The implementation of these three interconnected services can be considered a challenge from a technological but also a legal perspective. At pilot level, a simple prototype was first shown to the partners in which: (i) a price per spot was suggested as a function of the occupancy level in each area by using a simple algorithm (see parking monitoring service screenshots), and the correlation between the payments and the occupancy status was evaluated, triggering an alarm when they did not match (Fig.1). In this way, public authorities could activate generic corrective and enforcement strategies if necessary. Payment was articulated through a third-party platform.

Surprisingly, this simplistic tool has risen the interest of the partners and other company' stakeholders, pushing Worldensing to further develop the initial concept beyond the scope of Fastprk2: these three services have been internally selected to complete the final refinement step before going to the market (TRL9).

In the last months of the project, the following actions have been completed: (i) the front-end have been improved to become a pure commercial solution, (ii) the first demos using Barcelona as testbed have been completed, and (iii) the service has been modified to offer refined statistics of the legal offences going on and suggest actions to effectively correct them (Fig.2 & Fig.3). In parallel, the details of these three services are currently being evaluated by legal advisors through a DPIA to determine its adaptation to the GDPR provisions.

Fig.1: Pilot area in Barcelona. General view of the first version of the enforcement service in Fasptrk2. The red area indicates a mismatch between payments and occupied parking slots.

Fig.2: Pilot area in Barcelona. Demo of the new enforcement service: historical statistics of the offence are provided through a modified user front-end.

Fig.3: Pilot area in Barcelona. Demo of the new enforcement service: the system suggests different correction strategies to reduce the number of violations per hour, such as sending a public agent to an specific area.

As an overall conclusion, it can be said that several ITS haven either developed or improved during Fastprk2 providing enough pieces of evidence that the **Concept 3** foreseen in the EC-GA has been **achieved**. Nevertheless, the service development and implementation are the visible faces of any technology, for this reason, they will be continuously improved before the final market launch even though the H2020 project is formally finished.

5. Wrap up and analysis from the pilots

Fastprk2 is an applied project, whose validation has relied on the successful operation of different pilots all around Europe and the US. The overall functionality of the integrated solution is based on the achievement of three different but complementary Concepts: (1) new sensor, (2) platform and (3) services. After the pilots' campaign and in view of the results found and presented in the preceding chapters as well as the feedback received from the partners, the main conclusions, summarized in the following table, are drawn:

Table 10- Main conclusions reached after the pilot campaign

Conclusions	
Concept 1 (Sensor)	The tandem IR+magnetic sensor has the required detection accuracy under controlled conditions.
	The node is ready to operate in harsh environments which were banned for the former version of Fastprk (magnetic sensor).
	The final accuracy value can be jeopardized by external parameters such as bad parking spot marks.
	The node performance fulfils the expectations from potential customers.
Concept 2 (Platform)	Fastprk (data flow and management suite) has been integrated in a transversal platform.
	Parking data can be easily combined with heterogeneous data sources.
	The platform supporting Fastprk can be easily deployed and adapted to different requirements and scenarios.
Concept 3 (Services)	The first set of ITS have been successfully implemented as a proof-of-concept technologies.
	The new AI tools are powerful enough to predict the traffic and parking occupancy in cities.
	ITS have risen the awareness of the third-parties, but their final adoption is contingent upon the performance of Concept 1.

Going into details of the partners' opinions (*Table 11*)¹⁰, it can be clearly seen that **Concept 1 and the related services** are the **principal subjects for attention**. In this sense, it is possible to state that the final result of Fastprk2 is well-aligned with the market expectations, while Concept 2 and Concept 3 will need further development before a successful final commercial outcome.

Table 11- Third parties' feedback on the requirements of parking solutions: (left) all aspects, (right) services

Main Smart Parking Aspects			Smart Parking Services		
1.	Accuracy (up to 95%)	67%	1.	Parking Occupancy	33%
2.	Software suite	17%	2.	Parking Forecast	17%
3.	Other	16%	3.	Payment	17%

In fact, the pilots' experience has validated many points but cast doubts upon the market adoption of some services due to their practical complexity or the high cost associated. For example, the traffic monitoring tool showing real-time information in cities relies on a third-party data provider which can charge hefty. In the table below, it is shown how monitoring only 10 streets with calls every 5 min (parameters good enough for demo purposes) has an acceptable monthly cost of 344 €, while a real deployment in an urban area (200 streets with calls every 60s) drives up the service 34.388 € per month. This is a huge challenge since this amount would be hardly bearable by public authorities in times of budgetary constraints, and it forces us to reconsider how to offer such a service to the market.

¹⁰ Full details of the surveys performed to the pilots' partners are given in the deliverable D6.2.

Table 12 - Cost simulation of traffic monitoring service for both demo and real uses

INPUTS	
ENTER NUMBER OF STREETS	10
ENTER REFRESH FREQUENCY (IN SECONDS)	300

RESULTS PER MONTH	
NUMBER OF CALLS PER MONTH	86400
COST PER MONTH	343,87 €
RESULTS PER WEEK	
NUMBER OF CALLS PER WEEK	20160
COST PER WEEK	80,24 €
RESULTS PER DAY	
NUMBER OF CALLS PER DAY	2880
COST PER DAY	11,46 €

INPUTS	
ENTER NUMBER OF STREETS	200
ENTER REFRESH FREQUENCY (IN SECONDS)	60

RESULTS PER MONTH	
NUMBER OF CALLS PER MONTH	8640000
COST PER MONTH	34.387,20 €
RESULTS PER WEEK	
NUMBER OF CALLS PER WEEK	2016000
COST PER WEEK	8.023,68 €
RESULTS PER DAY	
NUMBER OF CALLS PER DAY	288000
COST PER DAY	1.146,24 €

Abbreviations

Acronym

AI
API
D
EC
EC-GA
EC-PO
GIS
IR
ITS
M
T
TRL
UX
VMP
WP
WS

Full name

Artificial Intelligence
Application Programming Interface
Deliverable
European Commission
Grant Agreement
Project Officer
Geographic Information System
Infrared
Intelligent Transport Services
Month
Task
Technology Readiness Level
User Experience
Variable Message Panel
Work package
Worldsensing

Annexes

In the next pages, images of the pilots are provided covering from the exact location, the installation stage and evidence of the data acquired with the new sensors. Further details are available upon request.

Annex I. Statement from AFAPARK representative about the operation of Bouffemont pilot

PIONEERING
THE INDUSTRIAL INTERNET

Paris, May 2018

To whom it may concern,

I hereby certify that:

- The technology developed in the frame of the EU project Fastprk2 (contract no.726607) has been tried out in selected locations under our control.
- The operation of the new parking sensors has been independently assessed by AFAPARK with the Bouffémont/Paris project, showing a performance in line with our expectations and the project's objectives.

Best regards,

Annex II. Grudziadz Pilot (Poland)

Location images (satellite & photos)

Civil work at the pilot location

Installation Process (sensors and gateway)

Operational Details

Real-time traffic flow in Grudziadz downtown. Data are provided by Tomtom

View of the sustainable traffic service: the pollution details of a control station in Grudziadz are shown

Annex III. Los Angeles Pilot (US)

Location images (satellite & photos)

Area 1: Wardlow North 3440 North Pacific PO. Long Beach Parking facility

Area 2: Wardlow South 3420 N Pacific PI Long Beach

Area 3: Willow St 2750 West American Avenue. Long Beach.

Operational Details

Parking occupancy in real time in Willow (area 3). Some of the sensors are FP2 nodes.

Pilot location

Annex IV. Example of data analysis (Barcelona pilot)

As indicated in Chapter 4, the new platform allows gathering parking events data for the ITS but also for the later analysis. This last point is quite important if meaningful mobility policies need to be developed at the city level. In this Annex, a simple example of the determination of occupancy patterns in Barcelona's pilot (university area) is given. Full details of the data analysis performed in the frame of the pilots' campaign will be progressively uploaded in ZENODO repository together with the raw data.

The pilot in Barcelona consisted of the monitoring of a few parking spots in the university area. Given the essence of this zone, fixed occupancy patterns were expected before the campaign.

Raw data coming from the sensors makes difficult to identify patterns and as a consequence define parking policies in the area. The figure shows mean occupancy values of each sensor as function of time.

The data aggregation for the whole campaign reveals interesting patterns: (i) there is a peak of events early in the morning with the arrival of students and university employees (5-9 am). (ii) a second peak of events is found between 2 pm and 3 pm ascribable to those students leaving the university after the morning sessions. (iii) Finally, late in the afternoon students and employees leave the parking area.

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